

Appendix D: Spectro-photometric SED fit

In this Appendix, we give some additional information on the SED fit.

D.1. BAGPIPES

When fitting the spectro-photometric data with BAGPIPES (Carnall et al. 2018), we considered the 2016 version of the Bruzual & Charlot (2003) single stellar population models, leaving the metallicity free to vary from 5% solar to 2.5 times solar. As mentioned in the main text, for dust extinction, we considered the reddening law by C00 or CF00, using a Gaussian prior centred on the value derived from the spectrum divided by a factor of 2.2 and 3.4, respectively, to convert from nebular to continuum dust extinction. Removing the prior on the dust extinction has no impact on the physical properties when assuming the CF00 dust extinction law, while produce a mild decrease in A_V and SFR when considering the C00 dust extinction law. We included nebular continuum and emission lines derived from a pre-computed model grid considering an ionisation parameter (i.e., the dimensionless ratio of densities of ionising photons to hydrogen) ranging from $\log_{10}(U) = -4$ to -1 . We let the stellar masses be free to vary between 10^6 and $10^{12.5} M_{\odot}$ considering a flat, uninformative prior. Finally, we considered a non-parametric star-formation history (Leja et al. 2019), considering three bins of 10, 20 and 70 Myr and then five other bins, equally distributed in logarithmic space, between 100 Myr and the age of the Universe (i.e., 1180 Myr). We assumed two different prior for the SFH, a continuity prior and bursty one (Leja et al. 2019; Tacchella et al. 2022). The complete list of parameters and priors is listed in Table D.1.

In Figure D.1 we show the comparison between the best SED models, considering both dust extinction laws and the available spectro-photometric data, while in Figure D.2 we show the output SFH. In Figures D.3 and D.4 we instead show the corner plots related to the two fits. These figures show that CEERS-14821 is going through a burst of star formation, as most of the star-formation happens in the last 10Myr. In particular, $SFR(< 10\text{Myr}) = 16^{+2}_{-2} M_{\odot}/\text{yr}$ and $SFR(< 10\text{Myr}) = 48^{+7}_{-6} M_{\odot}/\text{yr}$, depending on the assumed reddening laws, while in the other age bins $\leq 0.1 M_{\odot}/\text{yr}$. Overall, the SFR is lower than the values derived from the dust-corrected H_{α} line, but still consistent within 2σ .

D.2. CIGALE

We investigate the possible presence of an AGN using the photometric information, given that the diagnostics based on line ratios are not conclusive, using the code CIGALE (Boquien et al. 2019). The current version of BAGPIPES does not include an AGN component. In the fit, which is based only on photometric data because of code limitations, we set the redshift to the spectroscopic value. We considered a double exponential SFH with the addition of a possible extra burst 20Myr-old, which is motivated by the results based on BAGPIPES with a non-parametric SFH, and a CF00 dust extinction law with a slope of -0.7 . The complete list of the free parameters considered is listed in Table D.2, while the comparisons between the best SED model and the available photometric data are shown in Figure D.5.

We obtained an AGN fraction of $f_{AGN} = 0.22 \pm 0.27$, derived with respect to the total dust luminosity, which does not exclude an AGN component, but is consistent with a negligible impact. Due to the large number of free parameters necessary to fit the

Fig. D.1. Spectro-photometric SED fit performed with BAGPIPES. We show the observed spectrum (black solid lines), the observed photometry (cyan circles) with empty symbols indicating filters with $S/N < 3$, and the SED models obtained assuming the reddening law by CF00, solid red, orange, and yellow lines, and C00, dashed green, cyan, and blue lines. In both cases we show the models derived assuming different priors on SFH and A_V .

Fig. D.2. The SFH derived from the spectro-photometric SED fitting assuming the reddening law by CF00, solid red, orange, and yellow lines, and C00, dashed green, cyan, and blue lines.

AGN component, the stellar mass is less constrained than in the previous fit done with BAGPIPES, resulting in $\log_{10}(M/M_{\odot}) = 9.64 \pm 0.33$. The dust attenuation is large, $A_V = 2.8 \pm 1.3$, which is consistent with CEERS-14821 still being in the HELM selection (see Fig. 2). In the text we consider as fiducial the BAGPIPES runs, given the limited AGN contribution and because they fit the spectrum together with the photometry and they are based on a non-parametric SFH.

References

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- Leja, J., Carnall, A. C., Johnson, B. D., Conroy, C., & Speagle, J. S. 2019, ApJ, 876, 3
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Table D.1. Parameters and priors of the BAGPIPES spectro-photometric fit.

Parameter	range	prior	hyper-parameters
stellar mass	$(10^6, 10^{12.5}) M_{\odot}$	logarithmic	
stellar metallicity	$(0.05, 2.5) Z_{\odot}$	uniform	
ionisation parameter $\log(U)$	$(10^{-4}, 10^{-1})$	logarithmic	
$\log[d(\text{SFR})]$	$(-10, 10)$	Student's t - continuity Student's t - bursty	$\mu = 2, \nu = 0.3$ $\mu = 2, \nu = 1.0$
C00 reddening law			
$A_{V,cont}$	(0,6)	Gaussian	$\mu = 0.97, \sigma = 0.26$
$A_{V,neb}/A_{V,cont}$	2.27	fixed	
CF00 reddening law			
$A_{V,cont}$	(0,6)	Gaussian	$\mu = 1.1, \sigma = 0.63$
$A_{V,neb}/A_{V,cont}$	3.0	fixed	
reddening law slope n	-0.7	fixed	

Table D.2. Grid utilised for the free parameters of our CIGALE SED-fitting run.

CIGALE fit parameters	Grid values	Description
Double exponential SFH [sfh2exp module]		
τ_{main}	2000, 6000, 10000	e-folding time of the main stellar population model in Myr
Age	1000, 2000, 5000, 10000, 13000	Age of the main stellar population in the galaxy in Myr
τ_{burst}	5., 10., 25., 50.0, 100.	e-folding time of the late starburst population model in Myr
f_{burst}	0.1, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75	Mass fraction of the late burst population
SSP component [bc03 module]		
Z	0.0001, 0.004, 0.008, 0.02, 0.05	Metallicity
Nebular component [nebular module]		
$\log U$	-4, -3, -2	Logarithmic ionization parameter
Dust attenuation component [dustatt_modified_CF00 module]		
$A_{V, \text{ISM}}$	0.5, 1, 1.5, 2.5, 4, 5, 6	V-band attenuation in the interstellar medium
AGN component [fritz2006 module]		
β	-1, -0.5, 0	Dust density distribution parameter
γ	0, 2, 4	Dust density distribution parameter
Ψ	0.001, 50.1, 80.1	Angle between the equatorial axis and line of sight
f_{AGN}	0., 0.1, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75	AGN fraction with respect to the total dust luminosity

Notes. In this table we show exclusively the parameters we allowed to vary in our analysis. All the remaining parameters are fixed and their value coincides with the default ones assigned by CIGALE.

Fig. D.3. Corner plot of the fit considering the reddening law by C00, the continuity prior on the SFH and the A_V prior. In this case, stellar mass does not include mass loss. dSFR_i indicates the SFR in the i age bin with decreasing redshift.

Fig. D.4. As Figure D.3, but considering the reddening law by CF00.

Fig. D.5. Photometric SED fit performed with CIGALE. We report the observed photometry (purple open circles), the model SED (solid black line) with the different components (coloured lines). The AGN emission (orange line) is so negligible to be too faint to be visible in the plot.